

Relationship Between Internet Scrolling Habit and Social Media Marketing

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Abstract

The previous study has concluded that internet scrolling is required to generate business, and social media employs psychological techniques to advertise for business purposes. The primary objective of this study was to investigate the opinions and experiences of bachelor's level students on the role of internet scrolling addiction impact on social media marketing. This study applied the quantitative approach and the survey instrument to collect data. The sample population was two hundred bachelor's level students at Oxford College of Engineering and Management. A random sampling method was used to select sample students among three thousand students

The results show a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with using social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, there was a positive association between social media marketing and influence on chatting apps ($p < 0.05$). Further, the results indicated a negative association between time of activeness and the use of social media with social media marketing. This study's implication would benefit social media marketers, students, scholars, entrepreneurs and owners of social media marketing businesses.

Keywords: *Implication, higher-level students, Internet scrolling habit, positive and negative association, social media marketing,*

1. INTRODUCTION

The following topic, "Relationship Between Internet Scrolling Habit and Social Media Marketing", relates to the two independent variables internet scrolling habit (and social media marketing). Internet scrolling habit is the state of being dependent on a specific drug or activity, i.e., in order to examine different areas of a screen; scrolling is the activity of moving displayed text or graphics up, down, or across the screen (Wiederhold, 2018). The theme was a mash-up of numerous topics, ranging from scrolling habit reducing children's attention span to the relationship between scrolling habit and social media marketing. The issue was modified as a marketing student based on course selection and desire.

As a grown-up adult and a marketing student, I was always fascinated by how social media plays a role in reaching end users and how today's world's most pervasive problem, "scrolling habit," affects social media marketing. This focal point has created the possibility of going deeper into this subject. As a researcher, I was curious about how customers perceive social media marketing and how it affects their perception of a marketing brand. This research was an eager process to acknowledge the relationship that can be found between the two independent variables. The current scenario of the state depends upon our population using smartphones and the Internet daily, which results in marketers being innovative and acknowledging the current situation globally. This research solely focuses on the findings that help understand the relationship between those two variables. This research was held mainly because of my curiosity and the light leading me to know more about the two variables' relationship.

Internet scrolling has a positive as well as negative impact on social media marketing. Some of the positive effects of internet scrolling are that it lets the prospects get knowledge about the product or the services. It helps in online engagement, promoting the right content at the right time. Internet scrolling not only helps big and small brands creatively approach prospects with less monetary value but has helped every business flourish in the market with the help of social media marketing. (Cheung et al., 2020)

Every coin has two sides, so internet scrolling has its own drawbacks too. The major impact of internet scrolling on social media marketing is that the prospect is to be

conscious about their mental health, such as anxiety and depression, in the long term (Kwak et al., 2022). The mindless internet scrolling leads to a goldfish memory of the prospect, which leads the marketing sector to be quick and innovative while presenting their presence on the market to catch the attention of the prospects. (Stanton, 2017)

The topic itself is imprecise and broad regarding psychological difficulties and how everyone perceives them. The biggest issue encountered while selecting this topic was determining how to demonstrate that the two independent variables had a relationship rather than being both individual characters. Knowing and admitting how a person's mind works and how individuals perceive social media marketing was a challenge because "social media marketing" and "Internet Scrolling habit" are both individual and broader horizons of knowledge. The following challenge was to collect first hand data. My curiosity, trust, and motivation have come from my teachers, who helped me with this research. It has paved the route for mining resources for this research. People claim motivation occurs when you are over concerned with knowing how, where, what, and when an issue emerges. The same goes for the inspiration for this research. I've always had these questions on my mind, along with my professors, who have invariably inspired me, acknowledged my abilities, and trusted me with their resources (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

An objective is a concise statement outlining a broad qualitative goal designed to propel the organization forward in a desired direction. Basically, it asks, "What do we want to do?" A well-worded objective is time-bound (doable in a quarter) and should inspire and capture the shared imagination of desired study. The primary objectives of this study were to investigate the opinions and experiences of higher-level students on the role of internet scrolling habit impact on social media marketing.

1. To examine the opinions on the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media on higher-level students
2. To examine the relationship between social media factors and social media marketing

1.2 Primary research question

When a researcher carries out an investigation to collect original and first-hand data, it is called primary research question. The question that describes the main specific objective of this type of research is known as the primary research question (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

1. *What is the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors?*

1.1. *What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?*

1.2. *What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?*

The following null hypothesis has been tested in this study.

H₀₁: There is no association between scrolling habit and social media marketing.

H₀₂: There is no association between the use of social media and social media marketing.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This review was based on the relationship between internet scrolling habit and social media marketing, the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing and the association between the use of social media and social media marketing. The critical factor was to enlighten the previous findings on the relationship between internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors in high-level students. The review of this study is based on books, journals and a thesis found on various websites such as google scholar, research gate etc. A summary of similar findings is presented (see Table 1).

Table 1. Findings of previous studies on internet scrolling habit and social media marketing

AUTHOR AND PUBLICATION YEARS	METHODS	FINDINGS
Gomathi (2020)	Descriptive research design	The results found that internet scrolling is required to generate business, and social media employs psychological techniques. The results further show that the social media platform's "feed" feature, where users are continuously flooded with content, is built-in, and flow is constant and at a large scale

AUTHOR AND PUBLICATION YEARS	METHODS	FINDINGS
Lupinacci (2020) Azpeitia (2020) Bunce, Flens & Neiles (2020)	Quantitative and Qualitative research, thematic analysis and	The results acknowledged that social media draws interest and promotes active, measurable participation in an online community and mindless scrolling, resulting in a shorter consumer attention span.
Czmecci (2017) Huan Chen (2017)	Descriptive Qualitative research	The results show that the habit to looking via social media is not gender-specific; digital word of mouth is a must in social media marketing. To engage consumers of young age while scrolling habit, marketers should have pictures and some images.
Coker, Flight & Baima (2017)	Descriptive	The following writers concluded that the consumer has more control over the content.
Gaddefors & Tollqvist (2017)	Deductive	The result shows that the marketer can contain the consumer and build relationships with the consumer through emotional content. Three concepts must be acknowledged reasons for using social media, the customer path, and the intention to buy.
Alalwan, Rana., Dwivedi & Algharabat, Zarrella (2017)	Survey research methods	The research found that social media marketing trends are based on digital word of mouth, customer relation management, and performance. There is a waste of opportunities resulting from a lack of social media marketing awareness among businesses.

Different writers (Gomathi & Veeramani, 2022; Ludmila & Lupinacci, 2020) emphasized that social media uses psychological techniques to produce business; its platform's "feed" feature, where users are constantly swamped with content, is built-in, and flow is steady and on a huge scale to advertise. Similarly, the three writers (Lupinacci, 2020; Azpeitia, 2021; Bunce et al., 2010) have discussed social media drawing interest and promoting active, measurable participation in an online community.

Furthermore, mindless scrolling raises questions about whether it reached the intended audience and whether social media marketing techniques are effective in the eyes of scrolling habit in young consumers, as well as scrolling habit affecting social media marketing, resulting in a shorter consumer attention span. Çizmecci (2017) and Chen (2017) highlighted that social media habit is not gender-specific. Only young consumers and college students don't need to use social media marketing as an approved celebrity and digital word-of-mouth. Marketers must have some image to engage young consumers addicted to scrolling online.

Many authors (Coker et al., 2017; Gaddefors & Tollqvist, 2017) highlighted that consumers have more control over the content, and Marketers should be able to satisfy Consumers by building relationships with Consumers through emotional content. Consumer intention is the main factor in social media marketing, resulting in Three concepts that must be acknowledged reasons for using social media, the customer path, and intention to buy. The trend of social media marketing on digital word of mouth, customer relationship management, performance, and social media marketing issues are current indicators of internet scrolling. It is a waste of opportunities caused by organizations' lack of social media marketing understanding (Alalwan et al. 2017; Zarrella 2009).

The primary goal of this study was to examine the attainment of social media marketing among college students and determine whether scrolling habit is related to the trend of social media marketing among college students. The studies mentioned above are critical for anyone directly or indirectly involved in social media marketing and anyone who uses a smartphone daily. Being a marketing student who is always interested in technological advancements in the marketing field is represented in this study. The study is quite important in my life because it serves as a stepping stone for me in this research field. This research is very important to me since it provides an educational and life-changing platform for me to be heard as a capable individual.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research paradigm is connected with (beliefs: epistemology, ontology), theoretical lens (social science theories), methodological approach (Quantitative methods approach), and methods (the survey) of data collection (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Worldviews differ in social reality (Ontology), how people gain knowledge of what they know (epistemology), and the role values play in research (axiology).

Similarly, the process of research (methodology), and the language of research (rhetoric) are different elements of the four worldviews. Methods of data collection help inform the problems under study. This study has followed Positivist worldviews typically associated with a quantitative approach. The Positivism worldview focuses on

the consequences of research. The primary importance of the question asked rather than the methods to inform the problems under the positivism study. Thus, it is pluralistic and oriented toward what works, and practices are required (Cohen et al. 2011).

Quantitative research method

Quantitative research is a research strategy that quantifies data collecting and analysis. It is built on a deductive method, emphasizing theory testing. It basically makes my observations about something unknown, unexplained, or new and investigates current theories surrounding my problem or issue. Descriptive, correlational, causal-comparative or quasi-experimental, and experimental are four quantitative research methods (Cohen et al. 2011). It tries to identify cause-effect correlations between dependent and independent variables. This study has used the survey method of a quantitative approach (Winston-Salem State University, 2022)

The study uses the correlation method of the quantitative research approach. Statistical data is used to determine the strength of a link between two or more variables. Relationships between and among a number of facts are sought and understood in this design style. This approach identify trends and patterns in data, but it not go so far as to prove the reasons for these observation patterns because observational research does not rely on cause and effect. Only collected data, relationships, and variable distributions are embedded in this quantitative approach (Creswell & Piano Clark 2011; Winston-Salem State University, 2022).

The strength of quantitative research is more accurate and reliable data as it involves studying and analyzing the data in the form of numbers, not in texts (Winston-Salem State University, 2022).

The survey method

This study has applied the survey study, which uses a process, tools, and techniques to collect information or data from a certain designated set of people. This method allows me to gather data from a large sample size or research population, helps me improve the validity and accuracy of my findings and is a convenient method of data collection for the researcher and the respondents. The cross-sectional survey covers a series of

structured questions linked to the research that were closed-ended questions with rating scales and semantic scales in this study. The survey was conducted at the Oxford College of Engineering and Management. The total sample size was 3000 students, with 200 samples chosen at random from all semesters of all three faculties (BBA, BCA, and Engineering)—having 200 data points ensures that the results obtained from my sample are close to what would have been collected if the entire population had been measured. It gives all units in the population an equal chance of being chosen. (Blog, 2022). Data concerning this research was collected personally through a 5-point Likert scale (i.e., strongly disagree, disagree, I do not know, agree, and strongly agree).

Data Analysis

My data analysis is based on mainly primary research question entitled *What is the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors?*

Descriptive statistical tools have been used to analyze the survey data, identifying trends and relationships in currently collected primary data. It comes in four varieties. Measures of Frequency (count, percentage, frequency, and using this to show how frequently a response is given), measures of central tendency (Mean), using tool shows how an average or most commonly indicated response), Measures of Dispersion or variation (Standard Deviation) that show how "spread out" the data are), and measures of position (comparing the mean value of two independent t-Test) that score to a normalized score (Lab 2018).

The survey collected the bachelor's students' responses to achieve the study's fixed objectives. The BCA, BBA and Engineering department heads were first contacted by email. In the second phase, they were requested to provide their students' contact emails when they replied to this author's first email. In the third stage, the permission of departments was requested. Three departments agreed to meet them and discuss this research's importance.

In the fourth phase, students of different departments were randomly selected for the further process of data collection. When this author got information from different departments about students' information, a consent form was sent to participate in this

research. After the students' acceptance, this author decided to go for the questionnaire distribution. Before sending the questionnaire, ten students were sent the survey questionnaire to pilot it. After the pilot study, some minor correction was made and sent the questionnaire to parents by email. The total population of parents was unknown, but this author sent two hundred fifteen (N = 215) questionnaires to the students, but only 200 questionnaires were returned by the returnees (N =200).

The data was initially uploaded in the SPSS of version 26 and cleared the data. After clearing the data, the analysis began with the dimension reduction method. After this process, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to find the subscales of categorized variables in the Rotated Component Matrix. After that each variable of the principal component (subscale) was recorded further to calculate each subscale's mean and standard deviation. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical approach that allows us to summarise the information in huge data tables using a smaller collection of "summary indices" that may be more readily displayed and studied. PCA aids in data interpretation, although it does not always detect key patterns (Creswell & Piano Clark 2011). Principal component analysis (PCA) reduces the complexity of multidimensional data while preserving trends and patterns. It accomplishes this by reducing the data to fewer dimensions that serve as feature summaries (Lever et al., 2017).

The PCA found seven subscales and seven independent variables: screen timing, use of social media, social networking site, app guidance, *audience preference*, *time of activeness on the Internet and the interesting factor of social media* (see Table 2). The primary purpose of using the Binary Logistic Regression Model (BLRM) was applied to find the impact of the independent variable (*screen timing, use of social media, social networking site, guidance of app, audience preference, time of activeness on the Internet and the interesting factor of social media*) on the dependent variable (**internet scrolling to social media marketing**). The primary purpose of using the regression model was to find the association between the dependent and independent variables.

Table 2. Research questions, subscales, number of variables in each scale, and regression factors (N = 200).

Research question	Scales	Subscales	Number of variables	PCA of Regression Analysis
Main research question	<i>What is the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors?</i>			
First question	<i>What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?</i>	1. Youth screen timing	6	REGR 1: Youth screen timing
		2. Use of social media	4	REGR 2: Use of social media
		1. Social networking site	5	REGR 1: Social networking site
		2. Guidance of app audience preference	3	REGR 2: Guidance of app audience preference
Second question	<i>What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?</i>	3. Time of activeness on the Internet	2	REGR 3: Time of activeness on the Internet
		4. The exciting factor of social media	3	REGR 4: The exciting factor of social media

Five-point Likert type

The result confirmed that the percentage of female (67%) respondents is higher than that of male respondents (33%). Two hundred students (N = 200) completed the questionnaire and shared their opinion on internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors

4. RESULTS

Social media marketing (SMM) efficiently fosters communications between customers and marketers, enabling activities that enhance brand awareness. For that reason, SMM remains considered a new marketing strategy, but how it impacts intentions is limited. But, to date, a lot of research on SMM is focused on consumer behaviour,

creative strategies, content analysis and the benefits of user-generated content, and their relevance to creating virtual brand communities (Jamil et al., 2022).

Table 3. Mean, Standard deviation and Alpha value of the Internet scrolling habit and social media marketing on the relationship between them. (N=200)

Subscales	Mean	STD	Alpha	Variances	KMO and Bartlett's Test
Digital well-being	3.45	.770	.773	20.046	
Use of social media	1.88	.539	.60	11.455	.736
Social networking site	2.85	.741	.614	8.368	
Guidance of app	2.88	.821	.651	8.275	
Audience preference	2.51	.689	.633	7.907	.655
Time of activeness on the Internet	3.59	1.0867	.610	6.303	
The exciting factor of social media	2.44	.7014	.601	7.406	

For the result, we have a scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. As we can see from the tabulated data, the highest mean is digital well-being corresponding to $M = 3.45$, which indicates that the participants agree on spending more time on the internet scrolling through social media rather than engaging in physical activities, talking to friends, playing games, spending time with family, studying, and following international news and events.

The following measure of the variable "use of social media" makes clear that the majority of the research participants disagree with the statement that social media should be used for business, communication, education, or amusement. The mean value of 1.88, which is less (2), indicated that social media users disagree mostly on using social media for the following purposes: education, communication, business, entertainment, and news (See Table 3).

Similarly, the results and value estimation of the social media-related parameters are shown (see Table 3). The first tabulated mean value, 2.85, which is less than (3), shows that participants disagree on utilizing the social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube between 6 pm and 12 pm. As 2.85 can be rounded into three parts, most people believe that such social media platforms are used most of the time. Furthermore, with a mean estimate of 2.88 less than (3), it can be concluded that

participants are dissatisfied with being informed on how to use the application via the mentioned photos, videos, articles, and blogs. The mean of the data for this subscale is 2.51. Most respondents disagree on preferring to see the content of videos, pictures, blogs or emails. Following the participants' peak activity period is the next data set to be tallied. The participants agreed to use social media between 12 pm to 5 am and from 5 am to 12 am, as indicated by the mean computed for this component is 3.59, which is greater than (3), indicating that participants have a neutral response on being active at a particular time as mentioned above. The mean value of the next factor, which measures participants' interest in the service, product, and promotion, is 2.4483, greater than (2), resulting that participants disagree on being interested in the service, product, or promotion of any business (See Table 3).

The standard deviation, connected to the normal distribution, measures how far the responses deviate from the mean. A large standard deviation compared to the mean suggests that the mean does not adequately represent the data. (Collis & Hussey, 2014). As per the tabulated standard deviation beside the subscale time of activeness on the Internet, all the subscales range from .500 to .900, which is comparative good than the one subscale with higher STD, which has variation in answers from the participants. Worldwide, an alpha value that is greater than .60 is considered valuable. All the subscales are above or equal to .60, which is acceptable for data analysis.

4.1 Internet scrolling habit of the youth generation

The Internet has become an important part of the daily life of adolescents. Easy access to the Internet and its social appeal among adolescent males render them at an increased risk of internet habit and the associated adverse physical and psychosocial effects. There are four main themes from the experiences of adolescents with internet habit: reasons for internet habit, unmet social needs without the Internet, effects of internet habit, and self-control over internet usage (Rakhmawati et al., 2021).

What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?

Recent years have witnessed a dramatic increase in Internet use across the world. The Internet has become an important part of the daily life of adolescents. Globally, Nepal

is also heading to use more Internet, approximately more than 37.5 %. Adolescents account for Nepal's internet users' highest proportion (Aryal, 2019). The results of block zero models has been presented (see)

Table 4. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	5.468	8	.707	.035	.048	246.587
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	5.468	8	.707			

The findings show that analyzing the factors' influence on the model odd was feasible. Thus, according to the model developed (digital well-being and use of social media) for higher level students' internet scrolling habit on social media marketing experience, the student's own beliefs lead to application positively that participants are on their smartphone screen, demonstrating the value of an odds ratio was 1.157 greater than the students whose beliefs lead to the impact of internet scrolling through use of social media. (.655) (see Table 4). As Campman (2017) stated, Nagelkerke's R square adjusted Cox and Snell's R Square calculus to theoretically enable the value to reach one (1); therefore, Nagelkerke's R square is always greater than Cox and Snell's R Square. It is the reason for considering Nagelkerke's R square value in this research.

Table 5. Binary model to predict youth's internet scrolling addition to social media marketing (N = 200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I.for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Digital well-being	.146	.155	.892	1	.345	1.157	.855	1.567
Use of social media	-.423	.185	5.249	1	.022	.655	.456	.941
Constant	.744	.156	22.867	1	.000	2.105		

The result further indicates a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying the negative association with using social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.423$, odds = .655). The result highlighted that there was no association with digital well-being ($p > 0.05$) (See Table 5).

4.2 The use of social media during social media marketing

What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?

Social media is becoming more and more popular all over the world and in Nepal too. The need for social media marketing in Nepal is more significant than ever. Social media marketing in Nepal has multiplied over the past decade. It is about sharing information using the Internet through social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, etc. Due to easily accessible smartphones, people, from children to the elderly, are connected to social networks. Social networks do not seem to stop until the world exists because it offers many advantages (Aryal, 2019; Warokka, 2020).

Table 6. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	17.556	5	.004			
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	13.903	8	.084	.084	.117	236.115

The analysis presented in table 4 only focuses on the block 1 results. As represented in table 6, the Chi-square-tested significant values were lower than 0.05, indicating that the model with the independent variable was better than the model with no independent variable (Block 0). The second item to verify was the -2log-likelihood (overall model fit). It was helpful to compare different models and identify which model better explains the information. The comparison cannot be made since this study analysis a single model. Nagelkerke's R square value shows its effect size of .117 (see Table 6).

The result of the classification table shows that it is possible to observe that the model correctly classifies 70% of 200 cases. It is exciting compared to the rate of block 0 models, in which no variables are considered. This rate was 82% in block 0 shows that the validated variables positively impact the model since block 1 correctly classifies a higher percentage of 200 cases. Through the analysis, it was possible to verify that all variables were validated by Wald's test ($p < 0.05$) from the all-variable study. The results indicate that analyzing the variables' impact on the model odd was possible. Thus, according to the model generated (Social networking site, guidance of app,

Audience preference, time of activeness on the Internet and the exciting factor of social media) for higher level students' internet scrolling habit on social media marketing experience, the students own beliefs lead to influence on the guidance of application positively influence their engagement in internet scrolling, showing the value of an odds ratio was 1.547 greater than the students whose beliefs lead to the impact of the internet scrolling on social media factor (.007) (see Table 6)

The result further indicates that there was a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, showing the negative association to social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.345$, odds = .708) through being active on Internet (see Table 5). Similarly, there is a positive association between social media marketing and influence on chatting apps ($p < 0.05$, $B = .436$, odds = 1.547)

Table 7. Binary model to predict youth's internet scrolling addition to social media marketing (N = 200)

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Social networking site	-.290	.162	3.213	1	.073	.748	.545	1.027
Guidance of application	-.213	.161	1.754	1	.185	.808	.589	1.108
Audience preference	.021	.158	.018	1	.894	1.021	.750	1.391
Influence on chatting app	.436	.161	7.312	1	.007	1.547	1.128	2.123
Time activeness internet	-.345	.158	4.769	1	.029	.708	.520	.965
Constant	.771	.160	23.244	1	.000	2.162		

The result highlighted no association between social networking sites, application guidance, and audience preferences ($p > 0.05$). (See Table 6). Thus, the analysis presented focuses on block 1 results. As shown in table 5, the Chi-square-tested significant values were lower than 0.05, indicating that the model with independent variables was better than the model with no independent variable (Block 0). The second item to verify was the -2log- likelihood (overall model fit). It was helpful to compare different models and identify which model better explains the information. The comparison cannot be made since this study analysis a single model. Nagelkerke's R square value shows its effect size of .159 (see Table 7).

In the Homers and Lemeshow test, the significant value is higher than 0.05, indicating

that the model perfectly fits the data (see table 7). The result of the classification table shows that it is possible to observe that the model correctly classifies 69% of 200 cases. It is exciting when compared with the rate of the block 0 models, in which no variables are considered. This rate was 67% in block 0, which shows that the validated variables positively impact the model since block 1 correctly classifies a higher percentage of 200 cases. Through the analysis, it was possible to verify that all variables were validated by Wald's test ($p < 0.05$) from all analyzed variables.

Table 8. Summary table of block 1 models

Model	Chi-square	df	Sig.	Cox and Snell's R Square	Nagelkerke's R square	-2log-likelihood
Omnibus tests of model coefficients	24.252	7	.001	.114	.159	229.419
Hosmer and Lemeshow test	6.884	8	.549			

The results indicate that analyzing the variables' impact on the model odd was possible. Thus, according to the model generated (Screen timing, Use of social media, Social networking site, guidance of app, Audience preference, time of activeness on the Internet and the exciting factor of social media) for higher-level students, internet scrolling habit in social media marketing experience, the students own beliefs lead to influence on the guidance of application positively influence their engagement in internet scrolling, showing the value of an odds ratio was 1.567 greater than the students whose beliefs lead to the impact of the internet scrolling on use of social media and time activeness on Internet (.032 and .021 respectively)(see Table 8).

Table 9. Wholesome model to predict youth's internet scrolling addition to social media marketing (N = 200).

Independent variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)	
							Lower	Upper
Digital well-being	.191	.168	1.292	1	.256	1.210	.871	1.680
Use of social media	-.433	.202	4.577	1	.032	.648	.436	.964
Social networking site	-.288	.170	2.891	1	.089	.749	.537	1.045
Guidance on app	-.159	.167	.910	1	.340	.853	.615	1.183
Audience preference	.034	.163	.043	1	.836	1.034	.751	1.424
Influence on chat app	.449	.164	7.494	1	.006	1.567	1.136	2.161
Time activeness internet	-.375	.162	5.364	1	.021	.687	.501	.944
Constant	.816	.166	24.087	1	.000	2.261		

The result further indicates a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.433$, $odds = .648$). Similarly, the results show that there was a significant association between time activeness on the Internet and observing social media marketing, indicating a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$, $B = -.375$, $odds = .687$) (see Table 8). The result highlighted that there was no association between digital well-being, social networking sites, the guidance of applications and audience preferences ($p > 0.05$) (See Table 9).

The student's independent t-test results show that the mean score for boys ($n = 66$) on the first subscale audience preference on social media ($M = 2.578$, $SD = 0.598$) is statistically significantly different from that of girls ($n = 134$) for the same variable ($M = 2.378$, $SD = 0.723$), indicating that there was a difference in audience preference on social media content.

Table 10. Results of Chi-Square results

Table 8 Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.502 ^a	1	.019		
Continuity Correction	4.801	1	.028		
Likelihood Ratio	5.441	1	.020		
Fisher's Exact Test				.021	.015
N of Valid Cases	200				

The value of Pearson Chi-square is 5.502, and the significant associated value is .019 (which is less than .05). The alternative H_1 and H_2 are rejected as the Asymp Sig value is less than .05 in Table 10, which results indicate an association between scrolling habit and social media marketing and the use of social media and social media marketing.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

My discussion is based on the study's research questions entitled the association between the purpose of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing factors. Three questions have already been raised in this study. The independent variables

examine the relationship between online scrolling habit and social media marketing. This study aimed to learn more about the influence of internet scrolling habit on social media marketing among young people.

The survey variables were derived from the Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Later they were converted into subscales ranging from digital well-being to usage of social media, social networking sites, doom scrolling, communication and technology, apps guidance, audience preferences, influences on chat applications, social networking sites, the interesting factor of social media, personal influence on social media and internet time activeness.

The results indicate that the subscales' highest and lowest mean values were analyzed. The Alpha values of all the variables of subscales are above .60, signifying that the data collected was not a hunch, but accurate data was collected from the respondents. The significant value is compatible if the value is ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show that social media use negatively impacts internet scrolling habit. But the influence of chatting apps has a positive impact on internet scrolling habit and social media marketing, and we can analyze that the variable time activeness has a negative impact on both the independent factor of internet scrolling habit and social media marketing. Furthermore, we can analyze from the data that there is no significant difference between the subscale audience preference as the significant value is higher than 0.05.

The results show a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the results show a significant association between time activeness on the Internet and observing social media marketing, indicating a negative association with social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). But the result further highlighted that there was no association between digital well-being, social networking sites, the guidance of applications and audience preferences ($p > 0.05$).

Through the study, a t-test of various gender opinions on similar questions was also performed, and the results were nearly identical. Still, when it came to the preference of overlooking the content, there was a difference with a value of $p = 0.042$, which is statistically different.

Research question 1. *What is the association between scrolling habit and social media marketing?*

The results show a significant association between internet scrolling habits and observing social media marketing, implying a negative association with using social media marketing ($p < 0.05$). The result of this study is supported by the study of Koessmeier and Büttner (2021), who found an opposite association between internet scrolling habits and the attraction of social media marketing. They also found individual differences.

Research question 2. *What is the association between the use of social media and social media marketing?*

The result shows a significant association between social media use and marketing, implying a negative association. This study is supported by the study of Gomathi and Veeramani (2022), who found a positive association between the use of social media and social media marketing among the youth. Social media allows marketers to connect and engage potential customers where they are on LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and even some of the younger platforms like TikTok. Marketers can engage their audience with a solid social media strategy and the ability to create engaging content.

Recommendation

- Future research could focus on using the mixed methods approach to understand the multiple reality of the impact of internet scrolling on social media marketing.
- Other bigger sample sizes could have been used instead of just 200, and the results and answers could have been more varied and accurate.
- Another element that could improve the future study's outcome is the presence of people of all ages.
- Further research could focus on collecting data from larger sample size and area.
- Further, future research could focus on the income constraint of the participants more than age in the buying perception that comes with online marketing.
- Future research could focus on the Geographical advancement of Nepal with online marketing.

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